

CULTURAL SCIENCES

SOCIOCULTURAL PREREQUISITES FOR THE CREATION OF THE GERMAN EXPRESSIONIST THEATRE

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Abstract

By the 1920s, the expressionist movement had spread to many fields of the arts, including the newly emerging cinematography, but was more popular in the theatre. Defeated in World War I, Germany was in a political, economic, social, and spiritual crisis. The population is experiencing the desolation and misery of Germany. In 1918-19, Germany was involved in revolts and revolutionary coups, and hence, the Bavarian Revolution, the Bavarian Soviet Republic was a logical outcome. The revolution organized by intellectuals (thinkers) has failed. A pacifist movement-direction was created in art, it was a protest against the existing political-social reality. Artists, including playwrights, considered the way of inner perfection of a person as a solution. The main method has become the presentation of human spiritual feelings. Protest against the rapid development of technology is becoming one of the leading topics. This direction also expresses how a person becomes a part of the mass and loses his individuality. To preserve the personal, it is necessary to find the meaning of life. The search for the meaning of life became the main problem and the main issue of the expressionists, and the main goal was that a man should remain a human being. To save the humanity in a human being - became the slogan of the expressionists. The features of expressionist dramaturgy are similar to intellectual dramaturgy, a certain thesis, idea is given and the action unfolds around it, there are no individual characters. Expressionists believed that it is necessary to study oneself through observation. And to know the inner world, we have to trust dreams, feelings, visions, illusions, and mirages. Besides dramaturgy, expressionism prevailed in theatre and performing arts. The theatre refuses to develop a character psychologically, the main thing is to embody a certain idea from a purely theatrical point of view. For expressionists, the theatre was a kind of "spiritual brotherhood" and the audience was included in this brotherhood. With this, they opposed the theatre to dissociation in society and hostility between people. The expressionist direction formed at the turn of the XIX-XX centuries had a great influence on various fields of art. In the 1920s, expressionism became very dominant in German theatre and also had a great influence on both European and American dramaturgy. For example: Friedrich Dürrenmatt, Max Frisch, Eugene O'Neill, etc.

Keywords: Expressionism, Dramaturgy, Director, Play, Theater, stage

Introduction

Defeated in the World War I, Germany was in a political, economic, social and spiritual crisis. The population is experiencing the desolation and misery of Germany. In 1918-19, Germany was involved in revolts, and revolutionary coups, and hence, the Bavarian Revolution, the Bavarian Soviet Republic¹ was a logical outcome. The revolution organized by intellectuals (thinkers) has failed. A pacifist movement-direction was created in art, it was a protest against the existing political-social reality. Artists, including playwrights, considered the way of inner perfection of a person as a solution. The main method has become the presentation of human spiritual feelings. Protest against the rapid development of technology is becoming one of the leading topics. This direction also expresses how a person becomes a part of the mass and loses his individuality. To preserve the personal, it is necessary to find the meaning of life. The search for the meaning of life became the main problem and the main issue of the expressionists, and the main goal was that a man should remain a human being. To save the

humanity in a human being - became the slogan of the expressionists. The features of expressionist dramaturgy are similar to intellectual dramaturgy, a certain thesis, an idea is given and the action unfolds around it, there are no individual characters. Expressionists believed that it is necessary to study oneself through observation. And to know the inner world, we have to trust dreams, feelings, visions, illusions, and mirages. Besides dramaturgy, expressionism prevailed in theatre and performing arts. The theatre refuses to develop a character psychologically, the main thing is to embody a certain idea from a purely theatrical point of view.

The works of Franz Werfel, Georg Kaiser, and Ernst Toller took a prominent place in the dramaturgy of German expressionism. In Franz Werfel's plays, the split personality is the main problem. The playwright sees human misery in a split personality. In every person, there is a conscious layer and also a subconscious layer, the evil origin. Nothing shows us that a person can overcome evil beginnings, for good to triumph. Although Werfel is not a so-called forger of myths,² the

¹ Historians divide the German Revolution into three stages: 1. November 3-10, 1918; 2. From mid-November to mid-January 1919, fights in Berlin; 3. From mid-January 1919 to May 1919, until the destruction of the Bavarian Soviet Republic.

² A term introduced by Jean-Paul Sartre, after Jean Anouilh's *Antigone* was staged. He wrote an essay "The Forgers of Myths", in which he analyzed and established the essence, forms, and methods of existential dramaturgy.

symbols in his plays represent certain myths, a certain model of existence. Werfel believed that the transformation of the world requires certain mystical actions, and first of all, insight into the inner world. The playwright sees the cause of degeneration in the split of personality, in the conflict between the good and the evil self. With Werfel, the evil self overcomes the good self and he considers this to be the basis for the degeneration of people. According to Werfel, a person should not give way to his empirical evil self. The mirror world, which shows a person his/her distorted image, is not true; the good world is true. With Werfel, a person “wakes up” to open his eyes.

Georg Kaiser has a slightly different position from Werfel. He believes that it is necessary to give up technology first, that the misfortune of mankind begins with industrialization. The rapid development of technology has deprived people of the human nature and made them an appendage of a machine, taking away their freedom and turning them into slaves of profit. All this made a person lose his/her humanity. Kaiser thinks that each person should realize the crime. According to Kaiser, if we don't get rid of all this, humanity will not be saved. Kaiser is against industrialization. He wants to create a world where a person is not a slave, but a master.

Ernst Toller, the most prominent representative of German expressionism, participated in the Bavarian revolution. The playwright attended the premiere of his first play *Masses Man (Masse Mensch)* in shackles because he was in prison for being a revolutionary. The play is a typical expressionist drama expressing a certain spiritual condition of a person. The playwright wants to depict not the external world, what happens outside of a person, but what happens in the inner world of a person (the spiritual state of a person). Here the concept of a dream comes into play. The characters are abstract, the language is dry, intermittent and dynamic. The main problem is the conflict between the collective, the mass and the individual. The soul of modern man is chaotic, because he cannot understand what revolution is and what revolution has become. Is this horror justified? Each person should carry this in his soul and see it with his inner eyes. It is not only about the fight with weapons, but also about the confrontation of ideas, the ideological fight. What does not concern the representative of the bourgeois class is terrible for a proletarian. There is no time sequence in his plays. Real time disappears in expressionism. There is artistic time, which is the time of man's inner world. The main protagonist is the human soul that experiences what is happening in the play. And feelings are never logical, or consistent. In his dramaturgical works Toller tries to direct the action like human mind, where imagination and reality are intertwined.

Methods

The method of historical-typological and comparative analysis used in the article allowed me to investigate the influence of German expressionism on stage art, and modern theater. What influence did

expressionist theory have on theater directing, acting, and scenography? What traditional theatrical techniques did it adopt and what innovations did it introduce into performing arts?

Reasoning

Expressionism was created as a protest against the entire previous culture, which was dominated by the rational mind. The representatives of the direction believed that dominance of rationality had ruined humanity, so they thought that we should oppose our subjective world to it and only there we will be able to find on the one hand, the truth, and on the other hand, a solution to get out of the crisis prevailing in the world. Intellect has created technology, and technology destroys the spiritual world of a man. The salvation should be sought in the inner world of a man, in a man's ability to be morally perfect (the issue of moral perfection is considered also by Henrik Ibsen and August Strindberg). Nothing will help a person if inner, spiritual world will not transform. Expressionists are also characterized by the search for God (Kierkegaardian motifs).³ A man should find his own God (and not one that is alienated from him).

Expressive theatre is characterized by: a direct expression of an idea, abstract characters that are bearers of a social function. In dramaturgy, a person became an addition to his chosen profession. The objective world has lost its true sense, therefore the whole objective world has been deformed, hence objects in their works are depicted deformed. A person's spiritual world, mood, inner expression, feelings are expressed in this “distorted” vision. In the creative works of the expressionists, a great place was devoted to the unconscious, the loss of the inner integrity of a person, the split personality. Normal and dream scenes substitute each other, a split personality characters were played by two actors.

For expressionists, the theatre was a kind of “spiritual brotherhood” and the audience was included in this brotherhood. With this, they opposed the theatre to dissociation in society and hostility between people. In 1919, the Tribune theatre was established in Berlin and a manifesto was published, the important points of which were: a united stage and audience, active participation of the audience in the performance, and the main function of the theatre was to create and reveal a new worldview. In such a theatre, a director and actors were often assigned the role of a preacher. On the stage, the actor-prophet or poet-prophet had the function of shaking and awakening the public. Expressionist directors strove to create an illusion on the stage that there are no boundaries between things, that everything breaks down, that the world in general is collapsing. They mainly used light to express this.

Antitechnocracy was the main theme in the theatre as well as in dramaturgy. Because, the expressionists believed that technology was killing people. Symbolic images of poverty and misfortune, death and diseases, etc. were to be presented on the stage in a generalized

³ Søren, The Gospel. <https://storage.ning.com/topology/rest/1.0/file/get/6136016261?profile=original> (Accessed: 27.10.2024)

form. Expressionist directors believed that the performance space (stage, square, etc.) should be divided into two parts - the audience on the one side, and the so-called pulpit on the other, from which "preachers" preach to the audience-parish with a performance. The directors used symbols and hints to clearly present the general idea of the play. For example, a negative character should not wear a white suit, darkness on the stage meant darkness in the character's soul, the character's ascending indicated that the he/she had achieved his/her goal, etc. The props used in the scenery were also loaded with symbols and hints: a door - led a character to the abyss, into the unknown, a window brought him/her back to people, etc. Specific plastic movements were developed for the actors in accordance with his/her state. The typicality of the characters was indicated by the appearance, poses and costumes of the characters. Expressionist directors created a theatre in which everything was built according to the principle: no feelings, each actor should convey the idea and mood of the play to the audience. The individuality of the actors was rejected, feelings and transformation in acting were reduced to a minimum. Preference was given to plasticity, movement, abstraction, alienation. For example, worker characters took a typical pose for workers. Speech of actors was dry and intermittent, the dynamics of the movement was slow, frozen, each pose expressed a feeling or a social position. The movements were unnatural, mechanical. While portraying a spy, an actor was given large ears. The exaggerated shapes were distinctive features of this era. Later, Bertholt Brecht, along with other things, would rely on the methods of expressionist theatre and create the theory of anti-mimetic, epic theatre and the so-called "alienation" effect.

The first stage of German Expressionist theater is called by researchers "lyrical" or "provincial." "Provincial" because the directors did not stage plays in Berlin during this period. They worked in Darmstadt, Frankfurt, Cologne, Düsseldorf, Dresden, and Mannheim. Gustav Hartung (1887-1946), Richard Weichert (1880-1961), and Otto Falkenberg (1873-1947) constructed their plays as a monologue of the main character and a sermon at the same time. Later, political motifs appear in the theater of the Expressionist direction. Famous directors of that period include Karlheinz Martin (1888-1948), Leopold Gessner (1878-1945), and Jürgen Fehling (1885-1968). Among them was Erwin Piscator (1893-1966), whose directing career began with the methods and forms of expressionist theater and eventually created political theater.

The expressionist movement also influenced Georgian theater, both in dramaturgy and in directing, acting, and scenography. The famous Georgian

director, founder of modern Georgian theater, Kote Marjanishvili,⁴ staged several plays by German expressionist playwrights at the Rustaveli National Theater in the 1923-24 season (together with Mikhail Koreli⁵ and Alexander (Sandro) Akhmeteli⁶) and at the Second State Drama Theater (currently the Marjanishvili Theater). Among them: Franz Werfel's "The Mirror Man" (Spiegelmensch), Georg Kaiser's "From Morning to Midnight" (Von Morgens bis Mitternachts), "Gas" ("Gas"), Ernst Toller's "Masse Mensch" (Man-Mass) and "Hoppla, leHop, Weben). Expressionist plays were written by: Polikarpe Kakabadze, Grigol Robakidze and others. The following were active in theatrical art: Irakli Gamrekeli, Petre Otskheli and others. It is an interesting fact that in 1928 the famous Georgian writer and writer Grigol Robakidze (before fleeing the Soviet Union, he lived and worked in Germany until his death) published an article in the magazine "Mnatobi" entitled "Piscator Theater".⁷

Expressionist directors staged both modern dramaturgy and classics. One aspect, one idea was singled out from a play, and everything was adapted to express and convey this idea. For example, Leopold Jessner moved the psychological moments to the background in Shakespeare's *Richard III* performed at the Berlin State Theatre. The director used a staircase in the scenery, and a throne was placed at the top. Fritz Kotner's Richard, during the first and second acts, climbs the stairs as if his whole life will pass toward the peak. Finally reaching the peak when he thinks he has won, defeated Richard falls from the top. After the curtain closed, Kotner's Richard would come out to the audience and say, "This is the fate of a tyrant".

In the performances of expressionist directors, scenography becomes monumental and at the same time symbolic-metaphorical. The sloping walls used in decorations expressed despair, the fragmented, broken stage - chaos. For example, in one of the plays - *The Good Soldier Švejk* (based on the work of Jaroslav Hašek) - the rails were moving continuously. They used film techniques and film footage (they even filmed a street chronicle in advance especially for the performance) to make the performance more understandable for the audience. After some performances, the actor even verbally explained to the audience what they wanted to say, what was the idea they wanted to convey through the performance.

Conclusion

The expressionist direction, which emerged at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, had a great influence on various fields of art. In the 1920s, expressionism became dominant in German theater and at the same time had a great influence on both European and American dramaturgy (Friedrich Dürrenmann, Max

⁴ Kote (ful name Konstantine) Marjanishvili, also known by the Russified name Konstantin Aleksandrovich Mardzhanov (1872–1933), was a Georgian theater director, well known as an important contributor to the evolution of Georgian, Russian and Soviet stages. One of the most prestigious and professional of Georgia's directors, he was particularly famous for his lavish and massive theater plays.

⁵ Mikheil Koreli (1876-1949) – well-known Georgian director.

⁶ Aleksandre (Sandro) Akhmeteli (1886-1937) – well-known Georgian director.

⁷ Robakidze, Piscator, July, 1928.

Frisch, Eugene O'Neill, etc.) and theatre. It is also interesting that, despite the so-called "Iron Curtain", expressionism also penetrated the theater art of the Soviet Union, several interesting plays were created and performances were staged. Including Georgia, which at that time was one of the republics of the Soviet Union.

The expressionist movement played a great role in the creation and development of new theatrical techniques and forms.

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